

Rieko Kodama, the First Lady of SEGA – Part One

Andrés Domenech Alcaide

CoolJapan.es

Hello again, readers. On this occasion, we address you to pay tribute, through a series of articles, to one of the brightest minds in the video game industry—not only in Japan, but worldwide. In 2026, it will be four years since her passing—her death was announced in October 2022, although it had occurred in May of that same year—and many of you may have wondered why the 2022 Sega Mega Drive Mini 2 pays tribute to her, as can be seen in the following image, where we can read “In memory of Rieko Kodama”.

Rieko Kodama is mentioned in the credits of the Sega Mega Drive Mini 2 console.

Kodama was a designer and artist who worked on more than fifty video games, and also went on to become a producer and director, establishing herself as a true pillar of Sega. Through her work, she contributed to franchises that remain immensely well known to this day—several of her titles are included in the catalogues of the Mega Drive Mini versions, as well as in various Sega classic game compilations—such as *Phantasy Star* and the very *Sonic the Hedgehog*.

After more than three decades as part of the industry, she passed away still at a relatively young age. Enthusiasts who discovered this tribute on the console could hardly believe it, and some even assumed it was a translation error. Sega did not make her passing public out of respect for her family's wishes, and fans learned of this bitter news upon purchasing the console, later confirmed by Yosuke Okunari—who had been her colleague at Sega—when asked about it.

But... as Captain Nathan Algren —portrayed by Tom Cruise in *The Last Samurai*, from 2003— would say: “I will not tell you how she died. I will tell you how she lived.”

The Origins of a Pioneer

Born in Yokosuka, in Kanagawa Prefecture, Japan, on 23 May 1963, Rieko Kodama began her journey with Sega in the 1980s, and her career cannot be understood without the arcade giant. However, her love for video games dates back much earlier, as she was able to visit arcades in her youth—deeply rooted in Japanese culture—although it was not something she did regularly. Her first contact with arcade machines came thanks to her parents—who were also familiar with video games—who had machines in their own café, and she played classics such as *Galaxian* (Namco, 1979) and *Space Invaders* (1978, released on Taito/Midway/Atari machines) from a very young age.

During her teenage years, she showed a strong interest in advertising, something already evident during her time at secondary school. When considering higher education, she hesitated between pursuing art and design or focusing on archaeology, given her fascination with civilisations such as Ancient Egypt. This period of uncertainty led to several academic setbacks, but she recovered, regained her interest in advertising, and ultimately focused on graphic design oriented towards marketing, which she studied at a technical school.

From that point onwards, she decided to channel her interest not into promoting the work of others, but into creating her own, and directed her career towards design. She believed that within the video game industry she could create her own work, although she did not yet fully understand the specific roles within a game development company. This lack of knowledge about how video games were actually made—and what their creation entailed—struck her as a challenge that could help her create something unique.

It was at this time that her career became tied to the video game industry. While she was familiar with arcade games and gaming halls, she was less acquainted with the broader world of video games, and saw this then-emerging industry in Japan—following the major crisis in the United States that nearly caused its collapse—as both an opportunity and a challenge.

The Famicom—which was released outside Japan as the Nintendo Entertainment System in 1985—had only been on the market for a few months—since July 1983—when Kodama was considering entering the industry. The same can be said of the Sega SG-1000 (1983)—later adapted from a subsequent version known as the Mark III and released as the Master System outside Japan in 1985—and the weight of the video game industry still rested on the arcade market rather than on home systems.

In the United States, the arcade market was still dominated by companies such as Midway and Atari—despite the crisis—but in Japan, Sega had secured almost the entire market—although other major companies such as Namco and Taito were also present from the early days of the industry, playing a significant role.

Her Entry into SEGA

Kodama joined the company through one of Sega’s employees, who had been a fellow student in higher-level courses. As a design professional, she was responsible for the visual aspects of the games she worked on. Although she initially believed her role would focus on advertising and graphic design, upon discovering the video game design department, she found it would be enjoyable to work there. She thus learned to create artwork and adapt it into sprites—pixels—with the guidance of artists such as Yoshiki Kawasaki—a professional behind the sprites of *Flicky* (1984)—and her first work for the industry titan was *Champion Boxing* (1984). Other veterans, such as Yū Suzuki and Yōji Ishii, also helped her adapt to the industry.

Kodama worked digitally from the very beginning, although due to her background and experience—she had been drawing since childhood—she also produced analogue artwork.

On the left, *Champion Boxing*, July 1984. Character design was handled by Rieko Kodama, and it was also the first title to credit Yū Suzuki, another Sega legend. On the right, a brochure for *Sega Ninja*, 1985.

Aside from her enormous talent, Kodama was also completely multi-tasked due to small development teams and the short production time for video games of the era, sometimes working on up to six games simultaneously. By this time, she was already known as “Phoenix Rie” or some variant thereof—a nickname she adopted as a blend of her own name and a tribute to her favourite *Saint Seiya* character, Phoenix Ikki—since Sega decided to hide the real names of its developers behind aliases.

Rieko Kodama had just entered an industry almost entirely dominated by men, but, as she herself noted, this never posed an obstacle. She was never treated differently, condescendingly, or offensively—perhaps due to Sega’s corporate practices or simply because she was fortunate to work with excellent colleagues. Kodama also always enjoyed teamwork and loved learning from others.

The Growth of Rieko Kodama as a Creator

At the time, Sega’s research and development teams were divided into three areas: design (art in the West), programming (which also included those responsible for game audio), and planning (game design and direction in the West). Kodama contributed to character and level design, environments, as well as brochures, covers, promotional illustrations, and game packaging.

She not only provided her art for *Champion Boxing*—which launched just six months after she joined the team—but also for other well-known Sega titles such as *Sega Ninja* (1985)—*Ninja Princess* in Japan—where players follow the adventures of Princess Kurumi (くるみ姫). A run-and-gun game—a subgenre of shooters exemplified by franchises like *Contra* or *Metal Slug*—it allowed the player to throw weapons like shurikens which could be powered up, and even temporarily turn Kurumi invisible. It became the most successful arcade game in Japan in April 1985, and while its mechanics were based on well-known games like *Commando* (1985) or *Front Line* (1982), its Japanese aesthetic, Edo-period setting, and female protagonist—unlike other versions where she had to be rescued—were highly praised, adding freshness and refinement to the gameplay.

Kodama didn’t stop there, and went on to work on other titles still fondly remembered today—many of which remain playable, have been included in numerous classic game collections, received remakes or remasters, and even appeared in the Sega Mega Drive Mini and its second iteration—such as the classic platformer *Alex Kidd in Miracle World* (1986). This game, alongside *Wonder Boy* (1986), was Sega’s answer to Nintendo’s *Super Mario Bros* (1985). Originally conceived as a *Dragon Ball*-based title, it became a wholly original world after Sega lost the rights during development, blending platforming with role-playing and strategy elements.

During this period, Kodama also contributed to titles like *Great Baseball* (1985)—a baseball game, as the title suggests—and *Quartet* (1986), a four-player shooter in which protagonists battle a series of robots, defeating bosses to obtain keys that unlock the next level. Another notable game of the era was the shooter *Fantasy Zone* (1986), directed by Yōji Ishii, one of the Sega veterans who had supported Kodama since her early years in the company.

Fantasy Zone offered players a truly innovative artistic experience, moving away from the usual realistic sci-fi aesthetic common in other shooters. Instead, it opted for a fun, almost absurd style reminiscent of Konami's famous *TwinBee* franchise (1985), starring Opa-Opa, a winged egg-shaped robot facing a range of whimsical enemies. In its 1987 sequel, *Fantasy Zone II: The Tears of Opa-Opa* —ファンタジーゾーン II オパオパの涙—, Kodama was part of the development team for the Master System version.

Original covers for the Japanese Sega Mark III versions of *Alex Kidd in Miracle World* (1986) and *Fantasy Zone II* (1987)

Kodama was steadily making a name for herself at Sega, and she was practically receiving assignments daily, even if they were small; these included designing characters or assets, such as the dragon form for *Miracle Warriors: Seal of the Dark Lord* (覇邪の封印, 1987) and an enemy for the SG-1000 version of *The Black Onyx* (1987). In addition, she served as a writer for Sega's newsletter, *Sega Players Enjoy Club* (from 1988), which later became a magazine—one that even included interviews with members of the various development teams and offered tips on modifying Sega gaming systems.

By this time, anyone would have said that this artist had given all she could... but the best of Rieko Kodama was yet to come, and she would move from illustrating characters to creating entire worlds... don't miss it in the next article!

Sources

- **Texts consulted from:** Eurogamer, Sega Retro, Szczepaniak, J. (2014), *The Untold History of Japanese Game Developers: Volume 1*, SMG Szczepaniak | **Text created by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]

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- Originally published on CoolJapan.es on 10 September 2025 —*Rieko Kodama, la gran dama de SEGA – Primera parte*—
- *This version is a faithful translation into English by Andrés Domenech Alcaide*